

METHODS OF CREATING AN INFORMATIONAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Davletov Nurlibay Aymuratovich

Regional center of Public education of Karakalpakstan Republic

Abstract: *The content of the article mentions that the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process is the need of the hour, and the main tasks of information and communication technologies in the implementation of information and methodical support in the educational process.*

Keywords: *Information, technology, education, education, lesson, student, teacher.*

INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the educational process is not only to acquire knowledge, but also to develop students' cognitive abilities and gain creative potential. The main goal of all reforms in the field of education is to educate spiritually well-developed people, to improve the education system, to implement lesson processes based on new pedagogic and information technologies in accordance with the needs of the times. That is why special attention is paid to the effective use of modern computer and information technologies in the educational system. This is to increase the level of knowledge and skills in this field, to provide technical support for the educational system, and to create full opportunities to use the Internet in order for the pedagogic staff to use modern tools of information technology in the process of education. An effective result can be achieved only through

Without the use of modern methods of teaching and information and communication technologies, a teacher cannot achieve effective results in his professional activity

METHODS

However, it is important to choose the right purpose and content, methods and means, and organizational forms of education. With the increase in the flow of information and the complexity of educational methods, it is increasingly difficult to organize education in a traditional way. Information and communication technology tools are of particular importance in the educational process and provide extremely wide opportunities for the field of education:

- organization of differential and individual education process; feedback;
- students' self-monitoring and correction;
- use of computer and information technologies such as animation, graphics, multiplication, sound in lessons;
- to create skills for students to learn science, etc.

And information technology has its advantage in this respect. The presence of the opportunity to explain the learned theoretical knowledge in a practical way on the basis of technical means ensures more active participation of students in the educational process.

Receiving and assimilating information, effective organization of two-way communication (between teacher and student, student and student) requires high student activity. The main task of information and communication technologies in the implementation of information and methodical provision in the educational process is to ensure two-way communication. It is impossible to teach without feedback, without constant communication between the teacher and the student. In the effective organization of this process, educational motives have a special place.

Information and communication technologies, in turn, are one of the most important factors that create motives. Because the summation of information, visualization, i.e., the availability of various presentation options, the use of animations, and the provision of information suitable for the age and physiological characteristics of the learners, increase students' interest in education and the desire to learn. creates internal driving forces (motives). The content of the work carried out in this regard is to teach how to develop a motive and how to keep it.

RESULTS

Informatization is a whole set of tools and conditions for the development of information processes, it is a process that includes the creation of appropriate technical, base, organizational, economic, cultural and educational reforms, which creates wide opportunities for technological education.

Modern technologies that strengthen the capabilities of mankind in terms of information production determine the quality of the intellectual potential of the information society, and such processes ensure the regular development of the information industry.

Acting on the basis of effective use of information provides the best ways to solve the following tasks:

- processing of information about the source and the process taking place in it;
- to regularly receive periodic information about the progress of processes and conduct controls based on them.

The use of teaching computing tools, the assimilation of knowledge communicated to the student by the teacher and (or) information and communication technologies, and the student's re-creation of the learned material, applying it in similar (analogous) situations. It envisages the organization of activities related to education.

Although the use of this method with the use of information and communication technologies makes it possible to significantly improve the quality of the organization of the educational process, it is possible to radically change the educational process compared to the traditional scheme (without information and communication technologies). does not give

In this regard, the use of problematic and research methods is more justified. The problem-based method of teaching uses the capabilities of information and communication technologies to organize the educational process by posing a problem and searching for solutions to solve it. The main goal is to maximally help students to increase their cognitive activity. Based on the knowledge gained in the educational process, it is envisaged to solve various types of problems, as well as to acquire and analyze a number of additional knowledge necessary to solve the problem. In this, special attention is paid to the acquisition of skills related to the collection, organization, analysis and transmission of information.

The research method using information and communication technologies of education provides for the independent creative activity of students in the process of conducting scientific and technical research within the framework of certain topics. When using this method, learning is the result of active research, discovery and play.

The latest technical achievements often take their rightful place in the educational process, and information and communication technologies are no exception in this sense. Initial experiences in the use of computers in the educational process show that the use of computer technology significantly increases the efficiency of the educational process, improves the accounting and evaluation of knowledge, and ensures that the teacher helps each student individually in solving difficult tasks. creates opportunities such as.

Information and communication technologies are a wide-ranging tool for processing information in the form of words, numbers, images, sounds and other forms. Their main feature as a tool is the possibility of setting (programming) to perform various actions related to information acquisition and processing.

DISCUSSION

The use of information and communication technologies in the educational process opens up new ways of developing users' thinking skills and abilities to solve

complex tasks, and provides fundamentally new opportunities for the activation of education. Information and communication technologies make it possible to make classroom and independent training more interesting and reliable, a large flow of information to be studied is easily assimilated.

In conclusion, it should be noted that didactics in the environment of modern information technologies, the potential of wide-ranging types of educational activities aimed at effective assimilation of knowledge through the active use of modern information technologies, is directly related to the ability to receive and assimilate information. it's happening.

CONCLUSION

Among the advantages of electronic resources, it is possible to include information aggregation, visualization, that is, the availability of various presentation options, the use of animations, the aspects of providing information suitable for the age and physiological characteristics of learners. It is of particular importance due to the presence of an opportunity to comprehensively master resources by developing creative thinking, educational skills and competencies in students.

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